

Fostering Innovation, Integration and Inclusion Through
Interdisciplinary Practices in Management

Effective Online Brand Building Strategy in India

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ABSTRACT

Today's competitive world every small and large organization focused on online brand building. Companies are using brand management strategy in today's digital age are increasingly very firstly using through internet. Most organizations use of website development, blog, and search engine optimization, Social Media, Online Press Release, use of other marketplaces to establish strong relationship with consumers and build brand awareness.

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INTRODUCTION

Today's competitive world every small and large organization focused on online brand building. Companies are using brand management strategy in today's digital age are increasingly very firstly using through internet. Most organizations use of website development, blog, and search engine optimization, Social Media, Online Press Release, use of other marketplaces to establish strong relationship with consumers and build brand awareness.

Branding is set of marketing and communication methods to help expand organization and products and services. Branding is help to create good impression in mind of customers. The key factors for brand identity for brand communication, logo, trademarks, brand loyalty, and brand management strategies.

Statement of Research Problem

In the light of the above discussion and increasing trend use of digital marketing as motivated to Researcher to undertake the "Effective online brand building strategy in India"

Source of data collection

Secondary Data

The secondary source of data collection includes the articles in renowned journals, papers presented at conference proceeding, reference books, thesis, survey reports and internet browsing and websites.

Objective

To study which effective online brand building strategy in India.

Effective online brand building strategy in India-
Brand logo and tagline

Attractive and meaningful Brand logo and tag line is help to build brand and brand awareness. The design elements of a logo must play off the mission, services, and products of a company to deliver a solid return on your branding investment. eye-catching visuals and a repeatable tagline is play important role.

Website

Creating and maintain website is very important tool for business, Website optimization is important for improve performance in search engine and brand visibility. Website is help to reach globally your brand through internet.

Blog

Crating blog is one of the important ways to improve visibility online. Blogging help to improve search engine visibility. Blogging is help to cultivate relationships with customers and other influencers.

Content

Content is key of online marketing and branding, Creating good quality content is very useful to improve online presence. It is one of the most effective marketing strategies to promote your business online.

Digital Marketing

Digital marketing is process of online marketing for selling products and service using digital technology, on internet, Digital marketing is using on mainly Smart phone, Tablet, Desktop PC, laptop and any other medium.

Digital marketing help to brand awareness and online brand building. It's help to increase traffic and engage customers and increase sale and conversion.

Search Engine

Search Engine Optimization (SEO) is the process of increase your website and web pages ranking and visibility in search engine through organically unpaid results. Search engine helps to increase your website traffic and this visitor convert in to customer this is helping to increase your orders and revenue. That's why most of company's working on Search engine optimization (SEO) its help to improve website traffic and brand awareness.

Social Media

Now a day's using social media is trend in India most of young generation and people using of social media for communication and entertainment purpose, so many companies are started marketing activity to engage people and brand awareness and brand building through using social media marketing strategy.

Most popular social media channel is. Facebook, WhatsApp, Instagram, YouTube, Twitter etc.

Online Press Releases

Online press release is very effective for brand awareness, Press relapses help to additional coverage for your brand to reach globally.

Display ads

Display advertisement is one of the parts of digital marketing, Display ads are running on website apps, through social media, Google Ad Words for Display advertisement using format is text, video, Images and flash. Display advertisement is helpful for brand awareness and promotion purpose for product and services.

Display ads are compatible for all devices like Mobile, tablet, and laptop, desktop. Display ads help to online brand awareness.

Targeting Right Audience

Brand cannot have target all age group of audience, A brand have specific targeted audience like age group, area, and gender, It's helps to improve brand awareness and brand building.

Images & Videos

The content of the website should be in a form such as, video, image and crisp text with beautiful and attractive catchy fonts. Is helpful to attract customer and engagement purpose through different platform like social media. It's help to brand awareness and brand building.

Advantages of Effective online brand building strategy in India

Global reach without any geographical or time boundaries.
Helps build and gain trust of customers
It's highly cost as well as time effective
Highly suitable for targeted marketing with real time results
Helps to build credibility

Key challenges

Building a digital strategy
Creating a brand-portfolio strategy
More competition
Maintaining brand presence in market.
Financial challenges

Conclusion

In today's competitive world it is not possible to grow organically in very short time in online brand building in India. Digital marketing paid ads it's helping to brand building and brand awareness in short time in online market to reach more customers.

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